

DOI:

UNIVERSITY DEPARTMENT'S WEBSITE AS AN EFFECTIVE TOOL
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Digitalizing the modern learning environment requires using new approaches in designing websites so that to attract enrolees and stakeholders including students, parents, the staff, alumni, accrediting agencies, employers, etc. at higher education institutions. In this context the problem of designing a university department's website as an effective tool of advertising, PR and media communications is of great importance taking into account the current situation of the pandemic which has fundamentally changed the world since online learning and enrolment campaigns have become a part of today's life.

In the modern learning environment, it is the website that can impact peoples' minds as to their decision making of using suggested services or not. Any website is considered as a result of teamwork geared toward promoting its services and products. A university department's website contains information about its activity and staff. An effective university department's website is characterized by increasing feedback of learning process' participants, strengthening the department's credibility, save time and money for users, etc.

It is known that advertising and PR communications are geared toward building brands and organizing feedback with target audiences. But there is a difference between them since advertising space is usually paid, and public relations results are earned through providing the media with information so that to form a positive public opinion in different forms including press releases, pitches, etc.

There are a lot of special platforms for building websites such as Wix, Weebly, Tilda, Google Sites, WordPress.com, Jimdo, etc., each of which has its pros and cons.

In M. Ye. Zhukovskiy National Aerospace University "Kharkiv Aviation Institute" the Documentation Science and the Ukrainian Language department's site is built based on Tilda which allows creating different kinds of websites: landing pages, portfolios, online stores, blogs, news portals, etc. The block-based model which allows creating a website from over 550 separate professionally designed blocks simplifies the process of its building taking into account the purposes and tasks of its functioning. It is comfortable to manage blocks of the website which are adapted for mobile phones thanks to specially developed applications. This website builder has the drag and drops functionality that makes the service more convenient for creators. There are different tariffs for using Tilda as it is a paid service including a personal plan costing \$10/month which allows getting a custom domain and accessing to all blocks and a business plan for \$20/month with the availability of 5 websites and a possibility of exporting the source code that is important for instance, for transferring a website to another host. But there is a serious disadvantage of Tilda in the case of switching to another resource after the end of its

subscription since all the website's information will be deleted from the storage without restoring it when hesitating for more than 6 months.

The structure of the Documentation Science and the Ukrainian Language department's site consists of such headings as home, about us, information for enrollees, students, educational programs, questioning, science and projects, virtual tour around the university, students' living conditions in dormitories, gallery, contacts, news, etc. (<https://k801.khai.edu>).

One of the effective ways of advertising educational programs of bachelor and magister levels of the specialty in Information, Library and Archival Studies" is involving students who make their advertising works within learning separate themes of their academic subjects, in particular the theme connected with creating advertising documents within the subject «Documentation Science», «Advertising and Information Technologies», etc. Students of different courses make various types of advertising including brochures, posters, business cards, videos, etc. telling about their image of the specialty they chose. The best works are put on the department's website in the section «Why is it worth choosing us?» (<https://k801.khai.edu/#rec296806675>) and it is very informative for enrollees and their parents when visiting it. When becoming participants of building the website as authors of advertising work students promote the university department's website. Besides, students' achievements are also a component of the department's website that stimulates them to take an active part in the scientific and learning activity.

One of the effective means of advertising, PR and media communications is also a website's information about successful career of alumnus (section «Our alumnus», <https://k801.khai.edu/#rec304934963>) which attracts enrollees much more than reading official information about places of employment written in relevant educational programs. All the blocks are designed taking into account the main colors of educational programs such as yellow, blue, rose, lilac, emerald concentrating attention on the website's branding. The logotype of the website is also based on the main colors of educational programs. Color symbols are also a part of the branding of the website since, for example, yellow and blue are used for compulsory components of the educational program as the symbol of the Ukrainian banner, and rose and lilac are applied for selective components as symbols of realizing students' dreams as to choosing academic subjects they want to. The website has links to YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram, which help users to follow events of the department and otherwise, there is a link to the department's site on those media tools.

Thus, taking into account the above-mentioned it is possible to state that the promotion of the university department's website as a tool of advertising PR and media communications can increase the popularity and efficiency of department's activity as to training highly-qualified specialists in the field of Information, Library and Archival Studies who need to meet today market's requirements.